

Enhancing Public Health Insights Through Machine Learning-Based Sentiment Analysis of Vaccine Data*

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Abstract—This paper presents the development of a sentiment analysis model aimed at understanding public perceptions of COVID-19 vaccines. Leveraging natural language processing (NLP), the model classifies social media discussions into positive or negative sentiments, providing actionable insights for policymakers. The project integrates machine learning techniques, user-centric design, and robust quality assurance to create a reliable, accessible tool for analyzing vaccine-related sentiment.

Index Terms—machine learning, Covid-19, vaccine, policy

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, which began in 2019, prompted unprecedented challenges and responses worldwide. Governments increasingly utilized social media to engage citizens, who in turn expressed their concerns, opinions, and experiences online. Vaccines emerged as a cornerstone of pandemic response, sparking widespread public discourse. Sentiment analysis offers a valuable lens to evaluate this discourse, helping stakeholders address misinformation, gauge public sentiment, and refine outreach strategies.

Building on previous research (Zulfadzli & Haliyana, 2019; Jayasurya et al., 2022), this project aims to develop a machine learning-based tool to classify tweets related to COVID-19 vaccines. The tool not only provides sentiment labels but also offers visualized insights to assist health policymakers in addressing public concerns and shaping communication strategies.

II. METHODOLOGY

The development of the sentiment classifier involved several steps:

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

Datasets from Kaggle (FullMoonDataScience, 2021; Kazanova, 2017) were selected, containing labeled tweets for sentiment classification. Preprocessing steps included:

- **Removing Noise:** Elimination of URLs, usernames, hashtags, and punctuation.
- **Normalization:** Conversion to lowercase and lemmatization for consistency.

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B. Model Development

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm was chosen for its robustness in text classification tasks. Text features were extracted using the TF-IDF vectorizer. The model was trained on a dataset of 300,000 labeled tweets, achieving:

- Training accuracy: 79.35%
- Test accuracy: 74.14%
- F1-score: 0.79

When tested on COVID-19 vaccine-related tweets, the model achieved sentiment classification accuracy of 72.12%.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING MODELS ON
GENERAL SENTIMENT DATA

Model	Feature extraction	Train Accuracy (%)	Test Accuracy (%)
SVM	TFIDF/Lemma	79.35	74.14
Random Forest	TFIDF	78.39	71.34
Naive Bayes	Count/Stemming	77.60	74.56

Table 2: Hyperparameter

C	1.0
kernel	linear
gamma	scale
degree	3
tol	0.001
max_iter	-1

Table 3: Performance of SVM model on COVID-19 tweets

Model	Feature extraction	Test Accuracy (%)
SVM	TFIDF/Vectorizer/ Lemmatization	72.12%

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A two-tiered software architecture was implemented:

- **Presentation Layer:** Developed using HTML and Flask to provide a user-friendly interface.
- **Application Layer:** Executes sentiment analysis and displays results.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system successfully categorizes tweets into positive or negative sentiments, with the option for users to upload files or input text directly. Outputs include sentiment labels and downloadable reports. Policymakers will find the tool effective for gauging public attitudes, addressing negative sentiments, and refining communication strategies.

V. CONCLUSION

The COVID-19 Vaccine Sentiment Classifier demonstrates the potential of machine learning and NLP in addressing real-world challenges. Its modular design and robust performance provide policymakers with a reliable tool to analyze public sentiment, guiding effective outreach and policy decisions.

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